
¿A DÓNDE HEMOS IDO A PARAR? COMENTARIOS EN TORNO A LA PSICOLOGÍA SOCIAL, ACADÉMICAMENTE DEFINIDA, EN 1998

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Tomados al azar en la estantería dos números del "European Journal of Social Psychology". Se trata del número 1 y del número 6, del volumen 26, año 1996. "Handling of missing values in path models for opinions or attitudes" [El manejo de los valores missing en los modelos de trayectoria para opiniones o actitudes], "Observational evaluative conditioning of an embedded stimulus element", "Equality ratio equity, general linear equity and framing effects in judgments of allocation divisions", "The representations of emotions in groups: the relative impact of social norms, positive-negative asymmetry and familiarity on the perception of emotions", "Stereotyping and attitudinal effects under time pressure", "The impact of differentially valued overlapping categorizations upon the differentiation between positively, negatively, and neutral evaluated social groups", "Being different or being better? National stereotypes and identifications of Polish and Dutch students", "'The Battle of Westminster': developing the social identity and development of collective conflict", "Social representations of aggression: Crossing the sex barrier", "Negativity and potency effects in impression formation", "Creating stereotypes and capturing their content", "Expectation-based and data-based illusory correlation: the effects of confirming evidence", "The dilution effect: judgement bias, conversational convention, or a bit of both?", "Mood and the impact of category membership and individualizing information", "Probabilistic national stereotypes", "Study of some determinants of

social comparison strategies using a new methodological tool: towards a dynamic approach".

O miremos en las contribuciones al último congreso de psicología social, celebrado en Donosti en septiembre de 1997: "Subtipos e identidad de género", "Comparación entre dos medidas de identidad social", "Ignorancia pluralista, atribución de causalidad y sesgos cognitivos en el caso del racismo antigitano: una investigación por encuesta", "Validez de constructo de la necesidad de autorrealización en el marco del modelo motivacional de las características de la tarea", "Estructura conductual en deportes sociomotores a través del análisis secuencial y del análisis de coordenadas polares"....

Se cumplen 30 años del inicio de la "CRISIS DE LA PSICOLOGIA SOCIAL". Espacio en el que, como todos/as ya sabemos, se debatía intensamente sobre el qué, el cómo y el para qué de la psicología social. La vivencia, la implicación, el interés de cada quien que intervino en este debate, era muy distinto. En unos casos se resaltaba la falta de coherencia de la disciplina, en otros se ponía en cuestión la psicología social misma, en otros se planteaba la necesidad de dar un vuelco sustancial a las prácticas científicas... En fin, muchas aportaciones que en su acción lograron definir un espacio-tiempo para la reflexión y el debate, y para la definición de algunas líneas de salida que reunían un amplio, aparentemente, consenso.

La ojeada a los títulos que inician esta reflexión me hace pensar sobre el alcance y los límites de ese debate abierto, y sobre las presuntas consecuencias que de él se derivan. Esta reflexión es tan sentida como escéptica, y tan cínica como colaboradora.

A. ¿Lo que se practica guarda alguna relación con lo que se predicó?

B. ¿Quién está dispuesto o dispuesta a aparecer bajo la etiqueta de "Psicología social"?

C. ¿El grado de tolerancia hacia la diversidad se corresponde con el pluralismo que se detecta en las concepciones y en las prácticas?

D. ¿Es la aplicabilidad o las aplicaciones la propuesta definitivamente aceptada en nuestro tiempo?

"La psicología social convencional se ha ido alejando progresivamente del mundo que se supone tenía que explicar. Aunque no ignora por completo la temática del mundo real, la trata de una forma estrecha y conservadora, que abstrae a los problemas de su contexto social. Esto es particularmente cierto en el caso de las relaciones entre los valores y la temática tratada por la psicología social (...) El mundo no espera a la psicología social; las ideas de la gente cambian y están en movimiento, y la psicología social se queda atrás. (...) Si queremos comprender el mundo cambiante y en movimiento, así como sus valores, tenemos que situar a nuestra psicología social en una perspectiva histórica (...) La psicología social convencional es con frecuencia estática en un doble sentido: ignora el contexto histórico y congela en el tiempo al individuo. (Armistead, 1974, pp.127-128)

"Cuando se combina el afán por conseguir leyes generales con una concepción de lo "social" en términos de interacción entre organismos y con el método experimental de laboratorio, se termina en una psicología social que sistemáticamente ignora el contexto social en el que se da la conducta, y eso tanto a nivel de conceptos como de métodos predominantes. Esa es la razón principal por la que la psicología social psicológica está en un callejón sin salida. Con las mejores intenciones científicas, se ha quedado varada en seco al ignorar los contextos sociales que no deberían darse por supuestos" (Armistead, 1974, p.14).

"Confronted with this situation, some seek refuge in methodology and in the respectability that it offers, though they full well that this is not a solution. The fact that there are so few of us is also important: it is difficult simply to continue writing for each other, to become isolated within our discipline and to be only judges of wath we do, while neglecting what happens elsewhere. Anthopology, linguistics, sociology, psychoanalysis and philosophy claim our attention; their practitioners demand that we communicate with them. It is impossible to ignore their questions and also those of the students who insist on getting answers. Social psychology as it is today is not of much help in confronting these pressures. It is an inward-looking pursuit and its development has been characterized by a neglect of the questions from which these pressures arise; or rather, it has developed in reaction to other presures of which economics, behaviorism and industry are the important" (Moscovici, 1972; p.20).

"Our disciplines do not appear to the younger generation as desinterested and objective as we claim them to be. They have taken it upon themselves to remind us of the ideological implications of what we do and its role in the preservation of the established order, as well as of the absence of social criticism in our work. They

blame us for finding refuge in methodology under the pretext that using adequate methods is equivalent to scientific investigation. We assert that our interest is in the problems of society. They answer that we calmly ignore social inequalities, political violence, wars, underdevelopment or racial conflict. As far as they are concerned, we are safely ensconced in the 'establishment'" (Moscovici, 1972; p.21)

"The time has now come to revise these notions. Science is a social institution and, as such, it is an object of analysis like any other, in the same sense as experimenters and their subjects are engaged in social interaction like everybody else. But even beyond this, the real question is simple enough though fundamental: we must ask what is the aim of the scientific community. Is it to support or to criticize the social order? Is it to consolidate it or to transform it? We are requested from all sides to state our position on this issue. There is little doubt that academic peace will not be restored for some time to come and that ivory towers will continue to crumble, one after another. It is therefore better to accept this as a fact of life than to regret a past which, after all, was not quite untarnished" (Moscovici, 1972; p. 23)

"It must be admitted that social psychology is not truly a science. We wish to give it an appearance of science by using mathematical reasoning and the refinements of experimental method; but the fact is that social psychology cannot be described as a discipline with a unitary field of interest, a systematic framework of criteria and requirements, a coherent body of knowledge or even a set of common perspectives shared by those who practice it. It would be nearer to the truth to say that it consists of a movement of research and methodology which periodically attracts a collection of diverse interests that sometimes succeed in enriching it in new and unexpected ways; but a solid foundation for the future has not been laid" (Moscovici, 1972; p.32)

"The point I wish to insist upon is that our entire "scientific ideology" -to take up a term used by Henri Tajfel- is an obstacle to this kind of development in social psychology. Three aspects of this ideology are, in my view, particularly important.

The first is the predominance of a positivistic epistemology (...) Many of us work away peacefully in our own corners guided by the idea that it is essential for the moment to accumulate facts which will serve one day to build a conceptual structure.

In the second place, the neglect of theoretical activity results in a sort of *tacit compromise* whereby we avoid facing questions about the nature of laws with which our discipline is concerned and about their mode of validation. This is reflected in conflicts between observation and experimentation, and between the role of the "psychological" and the role of the "social" (...)

Last, but not least, the avoidance of theory and theoretical debate has also its emotional aspects. The social sciences, including social psychology, developed in confrontation with philosophy. As a result of this, there exists a kind of reactive fear of

indulging in “philosophical” speculation. Manipulation of ideas is therefore acceptable on condition that it leads more or less directly to experimentation or, alternatively, if it is capable of a mathematical formalization which, however weak or dubious, offers at least an appearance of “respectability”. Because of the prevailing insecurity, the milieu of the social sciences has become so repressive that it has made science completely uninteresting; the fundamental problems of Man and society are lost in a cloud of fragmentary “fields” and techniques which succeed in turning away genuine talent and in freezing all enthusiasm” (Moscovici, 1972; p.36-37)

Bibliografía

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